

Study on motivation and learner autonomy in learning English as Second Language (ESL) among Engineering students in Bhutan

Thinley Wangmo

Asst. Lecturer

Jigme Namgyel Engineering College

Abstract

The paper attempts to study technical students' perception towards language learning. The study has selected students from an Engineering college where medium of instruction is in English. These participants have more than 12 years of education in English medium and they are studying one English course in the college. The study employed a questionnaire as a quantitative data collection tool. The questions used Likert-type scales adopted from Chan, Spratt, and Humphreys with slight modification. The study chose the affective variable- motivation as it's a significant attribute in attaining learner autonomy. Learner autonomy is the ability of a student to take charge of their own learning. Language learning is not just a subject in their curriculum, it's a skill for a language learner to communicate in target community with intelligible native-like fluency. The findings indicated that learners depend on teachers to take decision regarding teaching-learning and classroom management. This proves that autonomous language learning behavior is least found among the participants. However, the learners do have a sense of deciding their weakness, working harder, and to take initiative in learning language outside the class. This study attempts to provide an insight on pedagogical implication in using learner-centered approaches and instill motivation among learners so that they can build autonomy for independent and self-learning.

Key words: Learner autonomy, motivation, ESL teaching-learning

Introduction

Second Language Acquisition (SLA) also known as Second Language Learning (SLL) is a process of acquiring additional language after the first language is established. It is a scholarly field of inquiry that investigates the human capacity to learn languages other than the first, during late childhood, adolescence or adulthood, once the first language (L1) has been acquired (Ortega,2013). Language learning is an innate ability of human beings but the process of acquiring L2 is observed to be highly complex. This interdisciplinary field emerged from the perspectives of linguistics, psychology, and subfields of applied linguistics-psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, and social psychology. SLA or SLL have evolved with different acquisition theories and in the last two centuries, it is observed that approaches to language

teaching have evolved. Due to emerging theoretical arguments among language learning/acquisition theories, language teaching approaches were developed by the various theorist. To name a few of these approaches are, grammar-translation method, direct method, audio-lingual method, communicative teaching method, task-based language teaching, and other second language teaching approaches. These approaches are interlinked and consider learner data such as the use of language in different conditions and contexts. The variation in language learning is influenced by variables such as biological factors, cognitive factors, affective factors, and socio-linguistic context. Researchers in the field of SLA states that L2 acquisition is influenced by variables such as age, transfer of L1 knowledge, cognitive style, linguistic environment, individual differences, and social factors. Although applied linguists combine the discipline to understand its implication in second language learning, Troike (2012) recommends that a satisfactory account of SLA must integrate multiple perspectives.

This paper attempts to study affective variables and cognitive variables, which affects individuals' linguistics and non-linguistic outcomes of learners. Learner's motivation is one of the significant affective variables in language learning. Motivation is a 'pathway' to change one's feeling, attitude, and behavior. It's a base to progress with respective endeavors. Dörnyei and Ushioda define motivation as “direction and magnitude of human behavior that influences the choice of a particular action, persistence with it and the effort expended on it (2011, P.4).” Thus, motivation in learning language has been placed significant by researchers, educationist, and learners. Similarly, Dörnyei and Ushioda as cited in Bernaus & Gardner, 2009 the role of motivation in English as Foreign Language (EFL) or English as Second Language (ESL) has been researched with a strong emphasis on its relationship to language learning achievements.

Learner's motivation is found to be a significant attribute in fostering learner autonomy. Benson (2011) shares an opinion from Rousseau and Illich that the idea of autonomy is a natural attribute, suppressed by formal education. Although a child is born with an innate ability to learn their mothertongue, as they grow and progress with institutionalized learning, they give up autonomy. Thus, it manifests learners' ability to take control of their learning. One such hypothesis placed was learners tend to exercise control over psychological factors influencing their learning. Therefore, motivation is one psychological factor that plays a significant role in language learning. Multiple theories are explaining the influence of motivation on language learning. However, this paper explores self-determination theory; which emphasizes the power of intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation.

The study is conducted on adult learners who are pursuing their studies in various engineering programs in one of the Tertiary institutes in Bhutan. Currently, there is a limited study conducted on autonomy and motivation for second language learning in the chosen context. Therefore, the study aims to explore the level of motivation engineering students possess in learning ESL and explores some pedagogical intervention in enhancing learner's intrinsic motivation and autonomy.

Literature review

Benson (2011, P. 58) defines autonomy "as the capacity to take control of one's own learning". He views that 'control' as the essence of autonomy in language learning. Learner's taking control orating charge of their learning differs according to context, times, and individuality of learner. Therefore, the founding father of learner autonomy Holec (1987) as cited in Benson (2011) elaborates his definition of taking charge of one's learning. Holec states that learner's ability to decide their learning such as determine objectives, defining the contents and progressions, selecting methods and techniques to be used, monitor the procedure of acquisition, and evaluating what has been acquired. In addition to Holec's definition Little (1991) added a psychological dimension- learner's capacity for detachment, critical reflection, decision making, and independent action (as cited in Benson, 2011).

While psychological factors such as motivation, emotions and beliefs are major variables associated with individual difference. Most literature related to autonomy has shown a significant relationship with motivation. Dickinson (1995) asserts research in motivation in general education suggest that motivation to learn and learning effectiveness can be increased in learners who take responsibility for their own learning, who understand and accept that their learning success is a result of effort and that failure can be overtaken with greater effort and better use of strategies. Deci and Ryan (1985) also share that motivation tends to be higher in learners who are interested in the learning task and the learning outcomes for their own sake rather than for rewards that result from success and who focus on learning outcomes rather than performance outcomes (Dweck, 1986) as cited in Dickinson(1995).

Ortega defines motivation as a desire to initiate L2 learning and the effort employed to sustain it (2013). Therefore, motivation is a 'pathway' to change one's feelings, attitude, and behaviour. Dörnyei and Ushioda define motivation as the "direction and magnitude of human behaviors that influence the choice of a particular action, persistence with it and the effort expended on it (2011, P.4)." Thus, motivation in learning language has been placed significant by researchers, educationist, and learners. Similarly, Dörnyei and Ushioda (as cited in Bernaus & Gardner, 2009) the role of motivation in English as Foreign Language (EFL) or English as Second Language (ESL) has been researched with a strong emphasis on its relationship to language learning achievements (2011). Although a child is born with an innate ability to learn their mother tongue, as they grow and progress with institutionalized learning, they give up autonomy. Thus, motivation manifests learners' ability to take control of their learning. In fact, it is a transitive concept where coaches and teachers can motivate their clients and students.

Socio-educational model

The socio-educational model of second language acquisition by Canadian researchers Robert Gardner and Wallace Lambert in the 1950s used Attitude Motivation Test Battery (AMTB) and quantified the level of motivation through effort, enjoyment, and investment dimension. To predict a reasonable proportion of L2 achievement level, the model included other variables/antecedents to form the structure of motivation. The model posits that language achievement is influenced by integrative motivation, language aptitude, and other factors. According to Gardner (2001), integrativeness is an attitude defined as a genuine interest in learning the second language to come closer to the other language community. Empirical

evidence proved that for some people a wish to integrate, in some sense, with the speech community of the language being learnt seemed to be more strongly associated with success, while for others a wish to capitalize on the usefulness of knowing a language within the learners' own culture was more effective. Thus, successful learners who attain native-like competence are likely to be motivated integratively. According to Dörnyei (2005), integrative motivation has three main constituents such as integrativeness, attitudes towards the learning situation, and motivation. Integrativeness refers to an interest in foreign languages and attitudes towards the L2 community and reflecting the individual's willingness and interest in social interaction with the target language community. Attitude is not only towards the teaching situation but also the language teacher and the L2 course; and motivation includes effort, desire, and investment towards learning. Therefore, Gardner identified 'integrative' and 'instrumental' motivation as two distinctions to study learner's language achievement.

Self-determination theory

However, the model was criticized for giving excessive emphasis on integrativeness, purely Canadian context, and being unresponsive to the wider development of psychology. Most importantly the earlier theory of motivation emphasized the quantity of motivation, instead of exploring the various qualities of motivation. Therefore, its shortcomings were addressed through Deci and Ryan's 'Self-determination theory. This theory focuses on two types of motivation namely; intrinsic and extrinsic. Ortega asserts that this theory interprets human as volitional beings' actions growth-oriented, that is predisposed to lifelong learning and development (as cited in Vansteenkiste et al., 2006). Thus, human behavior in this theory is guided by self-determination of one's action and activities. Intrinsic motivation refers to individuals' engagement in behavior that they understand as self-initiated by choice and largely sustained by inherent enjoyment in the activity. While extrinsic motivation refers to behavior as structured by a means-end, pragmatic-instrumental causation that is from outside. This means a learner motivated to learn a language out of their interest and to be part of the target community is intrinsic and learner acquiring L2 as part of the curriculum, to obtain good grade or get a good job in an international organization is extrinsic motivation. The binary concept of intrinsic and extrinsic is complicated by the human desire to feel related to the L2 community. Initially, this desire is external values or beliefs which gradually internalize, this is known as 'Introjected regulation'. 'Interjected regulation' also happens when external values are accepted and adopted as one's own and the individual comes to see the relevance and meaningfulness of an activity. However, an individual who fails to see any internal or external value of their actions is a case of 'amotivation'.

Empirical studies on motivation in the SLA field

The theory on motivation has undergone several reforms and studied on each antecedent on their chosen subjects. Noels, Pelletier, Clement and Vallerand did a study on the reliability and validity on the scale of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation for L2 learning (2000). Benson shares that way of learning a language and outcomes of learning effort is influenced by individual difference (ID) variables. Gender, age, language learning aptitude, personality, learning style, motivation, affective state, and learning beliefs are the ID variables that influence L2 learning. Although age, learning styles are innate and it cannot change,

the motivation, learning beliefs can be changed due to learner control or being open to change in context. Ellis (1994) as cited in Benson (2017) suggests that individual variables form a continuum according to how mutable they are. For instance, language aptitude is stable while motivation is likely to change as a result of learning experiences.

Similar findings were obtained in the study conducted by Noels et al., (2000). Their analyses suggest that learner motivation can be validly assessed using the intrinsic and extrinsic subtypes. Their study was conducted on 159 French-English bilingual students who are studying French as their L2. In the study, they found that each motivation subtypes correlate and influence one another. The instructional environment that is perceived to be controlling and thwarting self-regulation and autonomy erode levels of intrinsic motivation (Noels et al., 2000). Therefore, this study states the significance of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in the area of education. Indicates the relevant motivational principles in other settings that are in the L2 domain. Students who learn an L2 in an autonomous, supportive environment where feedback enhances their sense of competence in the learning task are likely to have pleasurable learning as it appeals to their self-concept (Noels, et al., 2000). Although intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is found convergent to other antecedents, Noels and her colleagues argued that self-determination theory did not accommodate societal attitudes towards L2 and its speakers, the influence of the sociocultural milieu, and issues of ethnic vitality and identification.

Dörnyei (2005) as cited in Koizumi and Matsuo examined attitudinal and motivational changes of 7th-grade Japanese students learning English over seven months. The student motivation appeared to stabilize as learners started to develop realistic goals (1993). Motivation as a variable in language learning is eclectic and multifaceted. Most research literature formed a tripartite L2 motivation comprising of integrative motivation, self-confidence, and the appraisal of the teaching environment. Dörnyei's (1991) framework consists of three-level: the language level, the learner level, and the learning situation level. This level is also considered as the social dimension, the personal dimension, and the educational subject matter dimension. The framework for L2 motivation below includes learner's background, their learning beliefs and teaching-learning aspects. Dörnyei as cited in Ortega (2013) reasoned that at least in the beginning stages of L2 learning, instrumental orientation and classroom attitudes influence the motivation of foreign language learners.

Self-determination theory, which explains the relationship between motivation and learner autonomy seem relevant in controlling motivation and influencing language learning. Ryan and Deci (2000) explained that the theory emphasizing the power of intrinsic motivation in learning and the importance of a sense of personal autonomy to its development. From a study conducted by Tomita and Sano (2016), intrinsic motivation is fostered in an educational setting which increases the levels of autonomy, relatedness, and competence. Relatedness here refers to a feeling of belonging through being valued and cared for by the teacher. Dörnyei (2008) states the significance of motivation and has been advocating that during the lengthy process of mastering certain subject matters, motivation does not remain constant but dynamically changes involving mental process, characterized by constant appraisal and balancing internal and external influences. Therefore, learners tend to shift the importance of teacher-related factors

from personality-based ones to teaching-skill based ones as they develop their proficiency. A study conducted by Fen Ng and Kiat Ng (2015) confirms that learner's motivation (intrinsic motivation) and the effect of perceived levels of teachers' commitment (extrinsic motivation) reconfirms that a teacher influences learner's motivation.

Methodology

Participants

The participants of this study are 72 ESL learners pursuing their diploma and degree programs in one of the engineering colleges in Bhutan. These participants have more than 12 years of education in English medium and they have or studying one English course in the college. They have participated voluntarily. The study also involved around 6 faculty teaching various programs in the college. Most of them are teaching general courses such as Academic skills, Dzongkha, Mathematic, Principle of Management and few with specialized courses; where students irrespective of their programmed needs to enroll in it.

Instruments and data analysis

The study employed a questionnaire as a quantitative data collection tool. The questions used Likert-type scales adopted from Chan, Spratt, and Humphreys with slight modification to suit the context (attached as Appendix A). In addition to that, reflective question or open-ended questions were asked to students as well as teacher to gain an in-depth understanding of the questionnaire results. The questionnaire was prepared in the google form and circulated online. The questionnaire for students is mainly to collect the perspective of learner autonomy, their motivation level and preferred learning strategy to motivate them. While the questionnaire for teachers is framed to collect their current teaching strategies, their perception of autonomy and student motivation. The quantitative data analysis is made to obtain descriptive statistics and qualitative analysis was made on the reflective report made by students and teachers in exploring the study topic.

Result

The first section of the questionnaire examined the learners' perspective on the responsibilities of learner themselves and their teachers inside and outside the classroom. For the interpretation of the data Likert scale of 'not' and 'a little' were categorized together, as were 'mainly' and 'completely'.

Items	Learner's responsibility (Mean)	Teacher's responsibility (Mean)	Learner's responsibility (Standard Deviation)	Teacher's responsibility (Standard Deviation)
make sure you make progress during the lesson?	4.01	3.88	1.03	0.87
make sure you make progress	3.78	3.31	1.05	1.00
stimulate your interest in	4.22	3.92	0.97	1.03
identify your weakness in	3.85	3.71	1.08	1.18
make you work harder?	3.96	3.58	1.04	1.11
decide the objective of your	3.71	3.93	1.03	0.86
decide what you should learn	3.51	3.86	1.03	0.95
choose what activities to use	3.53	3.92	1.02	0.93
decide how long to spend on	3.68	3.69	0.93	0.92
choose what materials to use	3.79	3.67	0.95	0.90
evaluate your learning?	3.68	3.92	1.05	0.98
evaluate your course?	3.65	4.14	1.05	1.08
decide what you learn outside	3.96	3.57	0.97	0.90
Choose learning activities in	3.56	3.51	0.82	0.84
Choose the learning objectives	3.65	3.51	0.86	0.79
Choose learning materials	3.57	3.68	0.85	0.82
Choose the learning materials in class?	3.47	3.57	0.93	0.89

Fig 1: Descriptive statistics of learners a teacher's response.

The overall figure portrays, its teacher's responsibility to take a decision regarding teaching-learning and classroom management. This indicates that autonomous language learning behavior is not at all found. However, when it comes to items such as 'identifying your weakness in English', 'decide what you should learn next in English lesson', 'decide how long to spend on each activity' 'make you work harder', and 'decide what you learn outside class' were opted mostly as learner's responsibility. Therefore, the learners do have a sense of deciding their weakness, working harder, and take initiative in learning outside the class. According to Fen Ng and Kiat Ng (2015), intrinsic motivation involves the enjoyment of learning a second language for its own sake without any external pressure. There are three types of intrinsic motivation namely; knowledge, accomplishment, and stimulation. Knowledge can be defined as motivation for learning a second language, exploring new ideas and developing knowledge while accomplishment refers to master a task or achieving a goal. Stimulation is related to appreciation, fun or excitement to perform the task. Thus, it signifies those learners possess the motivation to learn English.

The table below shows learner's learning activities and behaviors in and outside class.

Fig 2: Learning activities and Behaviors outside class

Fig 3: Learning activities and Behaviors in the class

While comparing the activities and behaviors of learners in and outside the class, the majority of students improve their English language by listening to English songs, watching English movies, and reading grammar books. While in-class activities, learners did not have much difference in their preferences when it comes to the option given. Maximum of them involved themselves in asking questions to their teacher, note-taking, speaking in English, and discuss learning problems with classmates. However, in making

suggestions to the teacher had the lowest ranking but proportional with other items.

Referring to learning activities in and outside the class indicates learners' motivation to learn a language, while due to still prevailing teacher-centric approaches the learner's perception towards decision making for their learning is found to be dim. However, to find the learner's motivation to learn English was asked to students of Engineering college, where English is considered a soft skill or secondary subject for them.

The following pie-chart indicates that most learners are 'well motivated to learn English' and very few who are 'Not at all motivated to learn English'. The reasons for not being motivated to learn English will be presented below the pie-chart.

How would you describe yourself:
72 responses

Fig 4: Showing the level of motivation JNEC students have in learning English

From a reflective response, students shared the following on why they are motivated to learn English.

<i>I am not interested since I don't have any basics in English. In the lower class, we are taught by NFE teachers. (NFE refers to Non-Formal Education)</i>
<i>Since I'm taking an engineering course, I'm not getting time to learn English so often.</i>
<i>Yes, it is universal language and we need it to communicate with people living in different country.</i>
<i>Yes, because it is international language</i>
<i>Yes. It's just beautiful sometimes. The ability and power of expression is just the difference of how we see our life and the world around us. If you have good language power then just a simple thing, any simple idea or a thing can be made to look as beautiful as it can get. And of course, the boring part is you need it to call yourself "Educated". There's more than just education in learning English and the earlier someone realizes that the more he gets to see the beauty of the Language .</i>
<i>Yes. The best thing ever loved in learning English language has always been the wonder of its construction la. For instance, the beauty of some of the arts in English is always worth counting.</i>
<i>Yes, I'm very much because English being secondary language and is used in most of the field as an operating language to communicate</i>
<i>Yes, because it has a lot of advantages to us in the future as it is the modern language that governs all over the world.</i>
<i>Yes, because I would like to improve my speaking where it will help me do gain confidence in doing public speaking/presentation.</i>

English is a medium of instruction in all schools of Bhutan and along with Dzongkha (National Language), English is also a compulsory subject. Failing to secure a pass percentage of 50% will lead to failure in a particular standard and student must repeat the class despite securing good marks in another subject. Students’ motivation to learn English before and now was examined. The result is shown below:

Compare your interest in learning English before and now
72 responses

Fig 5: Motivation to learn English before joining JNEC

Compare your interest in learning English before and now
72 responses

Fig 6: Motivation to learn English after joining JNEC

The graphs indicate that the average value of students' motivation before joining JNEC was 6.06 and 7.63 now. There is a slight increase in their motivation level and most of them shared that they are motivated to learn out of their interest, realizing it as a lingua franca in the international community.

The first thing, to satisfy job requirements is to learn English. Second, it's very exciting to learn English and lastly English is the only language which can connect people of different natives

It is mainly due to being:

- 1. Used in almost all the fields as a medium*
- 2. Subjects that we learn are all in English*
- 3. Used internationally*

The standard of language and the way it helps us to dwell to different world. It's a beautiful language to note down our thoughts in those words and magnify its effect. I just love to see how people express in many ways

Educational Implications

Dornyei (2001) states that the teacher is a complex and key figure who influence the motivational quality of learning and Ushioda (2003) affirms that teachers play a vital role in mediating the growth of motivation. Going through the evolution in teaching approaches; from rote learning to experiential learning, from classical humanism to progressivism or mixed-focus curriculum, and establishing a humanistic approach where learners are taken as ‘whole person’ indicates the significant role of a teacher in influencing learners’ learning preferences. Thus, the classroom experiences will determine the quality of learners’ learning experience and affect their motivation. A study conducted by Christophel and Gorham (1995) as cited in Fen Ng and Kiat Ng (2015) found a significant positive and negative influence on learner motivation. In their study, the teacher’s use of immediacy behavior such as perceived physical and psychological closeness between people positively affects learner motivation. Many studies on motivation also found that teachers possess influential roles and the strategies that are used by teachers in classrooms develop learner's realistic intrinsic motivation.

The statement below shows how a learner is motivated by a teacher and creates an impact in their learning:

I was interested before because I used to get influenced by the teachers who spoke very good English and I have no more interest further as I know that I can speak enough for my survival.

Having a good teacher. Surprising us with new and unique idea.

Some factor that can motivate me to learn English depend on teacher or tutor. If teacher have willing heart to make their student learn and improve English then I also get motivated.

Unlike in lower classes, the chosen college have adult learners and do not find a reason for teachers to develop learner's extrinsic motivation. Extrinsic motivation is external factors such as rewards or grades that motivate learners to learn. However, Vallerand (1997) as cited in Dickinson proposed that language learners with intrinsic motivation tend to produce positive learning results, while extrinsic motivation is more associated with negative learning outcomes. Intrinsically motivated learners retain the content for a longer period, and self-sustained.

Some of the way teaching faculty in JNEC motivates learners are to relate learning with real-life context since they are preparing to be professionals in their specific field. Teachers shared the followings:

<i>Teach the learners through citing realistic examples, Connect the lessons to the real work-life scenario, financial incentives can also motivate students too, narrate a story or incidences that are related to the subjects, never start the session directly in the class, share something beyond the subjects before the session</i>
<i>The first step is to establish a positive teacher-student relationship in which teachers are respected and students are valued.</i>
<i>The following are some ways to motivate the learners: 1. Develop meaningful and respectful relationships with your students. 2. Establish high expectations and establish clear goals. 3 Being inspirational. 4. Talk story about successful persons to motivate the learners.</i>
<i>- be a good listener, - be exemplary to be copied from, - be an enthusiast</i>
<i>Students can be motivated by providing a conducive learning environment, establishing a healthy relationship with them, preparing lesson as per the students' competency level, engaging all the students in active learning and recognizing the little effort put by the students.</i>
<i>Be inspiring, build a respectful relationship with learners, design clear teaching learning goals, be open to their opinion and views.</i>
<i>In 1 hour, session of class, avoid too much emphasis on the subject alone throughout the lesson. Design lesson in a way, it includes activities (individual/group), links the lesson to apply in future or its value and related to a real-world situation. Sharing inspiring stories.</i>
<i>To plan an exciting session, incorporate different teaching-learning methods, teach in a way they enjoy learning by making it fun, introducing a new game or giving the new information.</i>

Referring to the reflective response of learners in learning the English language it is observed that most are motivated to learn out of their interest, realizing the need in communicating with the international community and to express effectively. They also shared that teacher do influence them motivation to learn the language. While teachers attempt to motivate learners by creating meaningful learning, relating the lesson to the real-life scenario, establish a positive relationship, and engaging learner in learner-based activities.

Conclusion

Motivation is an individual human behavior that creates complexity and considers subjective. Therefore, researchers have found multiple theories in studying motivation related to learner autonomy. However, this study is to examine the level of motivation engineering students have in learning the English language, their perception towards learning autonomously, some of the preferred activities they do to study the English language and the role of teachers in motivating them. Further study can be conducted to

study learner motivation covering the aspect of other theories such as attribution theory; which considers learner's ability, task difficulty, effort, and luck as attribution to success and failure in learning. However, for this study, it is evident that learners in Engineering college is motivated to learn English and it is not the reward or awards that influence their motivation. Teachers play a significant role in improving their level of motivation through their pedagogical intervention.

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